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Dual cropping of *Azolla* substitutes for second topdressing of N in rice

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The integrated use of bioorganic and inorganic sources of N is essential in achieving higher N use efficiency, increased yield, and sustained soil fertility. Biological N₂ fixation (BNF) through the *Azolla-Anabaena* complex is considered to be a potentially useful system because it contributes 40–60 kg N ha⁻¹ in addition to increasing rice yield at a comparatively low cost. Whenever bioinoculants are used, fertilizer N should be reduced by 25%. So far, no specific study has been conducted to determine the suitable time for input reduction. This study was conducted to learn whether N can be reduced uniformly during all application times or if one topdressing can be skipped.

Field experiments were conducted during the 1995 and 1996 kuruvai (June–September) and thaladi (October–March) seasons. The control treatment consisted of applying 12.5 kg ha⁻¹ of urea basally and 25 kg ha⁻¹ as topdressing at 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DAT) (Table 1). *Azolla microphylla* was applied in combination with the elimination of any one of the three topdressings as well as the uniform reduction in N in all applications or at basal application only. Phosphorus as single superphosphate and potassium as muriate of potash were applied basally at 50 kg ha⁻¹ each. Fresh fronds of *A. microphylla* were inoculated at 1 t ha⁻¹ at 10 DAT and

incorporated at 30 DAT. A layer of *Azolla* covering a hectare of rice field supplies about 25–30 kg N ha⁻¹. Trials were conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil samples were taken at 0, 35, and 65 DAT for available N estimation and grain yield was recorded at harvest.

Results clearly revealed that dual cropping of *A. microphylla* with rice enhanced soil available N status and grain yield. Available N content increased in the soil because of the incorporation of *A. microphylla* (Table 1). N increase was evident in the treatment where the second topdressing was skipped. *Azolla* is usually incorporated at 30 DAT, which coincides with the second topdressing of N, releasing more ammoniacal N at this time because of *Azolla* mineralization. Furthermore, *Azolla*

excretes ammonia continuously in floodwater during growth. Dual cropping of *Azolla* with rice always resulted in a yield increase (Table 2). Grain yield was greater, however, when the second topdressing of N was skipped, with 6.2 and 5.6 t ha⁻¹ during the 1995 and 1996 kuruvai seasons, respectively. A similar trend was seen in the thaladi seasons. The yield increase may be due to the release of micronutrients such as Ca, Mg, and S upon decomposition of *Azolla*. Moreover, the development of a thick mat of *Azolla* successfully suppressed weeds in rice fields.

At 30 DAT when *Azolla* is incorporated, topdressing can therefore be skipped. One less topdressing means less fertilizer and labor costs. The study clearly indicated the possibility of reducing fertilizer N when *Azolla* is raised as a dual crop.

Table 2. Effect of *Azolla* dual cropping on rice yield (t ha⁻¹).^a

N treatment (kg ha ⁻¹)					Kuruvai		Thaladi	
0 DAT	15 DAT	30 DAT	45 DAT	<i>Azolla</i>	1995	1996	1995	1996
50	25	25	25	–	5.3 c	4.2 c	4.6 d	4.5 d
50	–	25	25	+	5.9 ab	5.3 ab	5.4 ab	5.3 b
50	25	–	25	+	6.2 a	5.6 a	5.7 a	5.6 a
50	25	25	–	+	5.8 b	5.3 ab	5.2 bc	5.1 bc
40	20	20	20	+	5.9 ab	5.2 ab	5.2 bc	5.1 bc
25	25	25	25	+	5.7 bc	4.9 b	5.2 bc	5.1 c
12.5	25	25	25	+	5.6 bc	4.9 b	5.0 c	5.0 c

^aSame letters denote parity among respective treatments using LSD.

Table 1. Effect of *Azolla* dual cropping on soil available N status (kg ha⁻¹).

N treatment ^a (kg ha ⁻¹)					Kuruvai						Thaladi									
					1995			1996			1995			1996						
0 DAT	15 DAT	30 DAT	45 DAT	<i>Azolla</i>	0 DAT	35 DAT	65 DAT	0 DAT	35 DAT	65 DAT	0 DAT	35 DAT	65 DAT	0 DAT	35 DAT	65 DAT				
50	25	25	25	–	90.7	130.2	135.4	91.0	133.0	145.6	96.6	120.4	135.8	95.8	126.0	130.2				
50	–	25	25	+	141.4	149.8		140.0	151.2		127.4	142.8		131.6	138.6					
50	25	–	25	+	148.4	155.2		147.0	156.8		130.2	148.4		135.8	142.8					
50	25	25	–	+	134.4	145.4		135.8	154.0		126.0	138.6		132.5	137.5					
40	20	20	20	+	133.0	142.8		142.8	142.8		126.0	140.0		128.6	134.4					
25	25	25	25	+	131.6	140.0		123.2	149.8		127.4	141.4		130.2	136.4					
12.5	25	25	25	+	131.6	137.2		128.8	147.0		124.6	138.6		131.6	137.5					
LSD (0.05)					5.38		9.63		6.01		7.96		4.99		4.05		7.67		6.41	

^a+ or – indicates presence or absence of treatment, respectively. DAT = days after transplanting.